

Notes

Polarographic Behaviour of the Complexes Formed by Pb(II) and Cd(II) with Nicotinate Ions

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Manuscript recied 15 November 1976, revised 27 March 1978,
accepted 17 May 1978

Pb(II) and **Cd(II)** form complexes with a number of ligands¹⁻⁴. The electrochemical behaviour of the complexes formed by lead and cadmium with formate, glycolate, salicylate, benzoate and phthalate⁵⁻¹⁰ have been studied by Jain and Gaur. The present paper deals with the determination of the formation constants of the complexes formed by Pb(II) and Cd(II) with nicotinate ions polarographically.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used. The solutions of metal ions were prepared from their nitrates. Sodium perchlorate was used to keep constant ionic strength ($\mu=1.0$), sodium nicotinate as the complexing agent and Triton-x100 as maxima suppressor. The pH of the solutions was kept at 6.6 ± 0.1 and measured by Toshniwal pH meter. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m=2.9$ mg/sec. and $t=2.84$ sec. (open circuit). The H-type cell with agar-agar bridge saturated with NaCl was used in all measurements. The temperature was kept constant at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with the help of a Haake type ultra thermostat.

Results and Discussion

In each case, a single well defined reduction wave appeared, whose half wave potential was found to shift towards more negative side and the diffusion current was found to decrease with the increasing concentration of nicotinate ion. The above results indicated complex formation between Cd(II) and Pb(II) with nicotinate ions. The plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ as well as i_d vs C_M (C_M is metal ion concentration) were linear and passing through origin, thereby showing the reduction process to be diffusion controlled.

The plots of $\log i/(i_d-i)$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ were found to be linear with a slope of the order of 31 ± 2 mV in case of Cd(II) and Pb(II), indicating reversibility of electrode process involving two electrons. The plots of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs $-\log C_X$ (where C_X is the nicotinate ion concentration) were found to be smooth curves showing the formation of two or more complex species which were in equilibrium. The formation constants have been calculated by DeFord and Hume's¹¹ treatment for consecutive complex formation. Experimentally determined values of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and diffusion currents gave the values of $F_0([X])$ for each system and plots of $F_0([X])$ vs C_X gave a smooth curve, again confirming the formation of two or more complexes. Formation constants have been calculated by extrapolating the curve of $F_j([X])$ vs C_X to zero ligand concentration. The polarographic characteristics and $F_j([X])$ values for both the systems have been incorporated in Tables 1 & 2.

TABLE 1 — POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_j([X])$ VALUES FOR Cd(II)-NICOTINATE COMPLEXES.

C_X (Moles)	i_d (Divs.)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (-V vs SCE)	$F_0([X])$	$F_1([X])$	$F_2([X])$	$F_3([X])$
0.00	81.50	0.6000	—	—	—	—
0.05	73.00	0.6090	2.23	24.56	91.2	—
0.10	68.75	0.6165	4.21	32.07	120.7	807
0.15	66.00	0.6247	8.22	48.15	187.7	985
0.20	62.25	0.6310	14.17	65.85	228.5	942
0.25	62.50	0.6370	22.31	85.24	260.5	884
0.30	60.25	0.6420	33.98	109.93	299.8	866
0.35	57.75	0.6460	48.18	134.80	328.0	823
0.40	56.25	0.6510	72.63	179.07	397.5	894
0.50	50.50	0.6595	155.30	308.60	680.4	1074

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TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_j([X])$ FUNCTIONS FOR Pb(II)-NICOTINATE COMPLEXES

C_{∞} (Moles)	i_d (Divs.)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (-V vs SCE)	$F_0([X])$	$F_1([X])$	$F_2([X])$
0.00	88.25	0.4105	—	—	—
0.05	79.00	0.4235	3.03	40.6	477.4
0.10	75.50	0.4335	6.83	58.3	308.0
0.15	70.50	0.4415	13.52	83.5	443.3
0.20	70.50	0.4465	19.84	94.2	383.5
0.25	70.50	0.4520	30.04	116.2	394.0
0.30	68.25	0.4565	44.15	143.8	421.0
0.35	67.00	0.4600	58.83	165.2	422.0
0.40	64.00	0.4630	77.54	191.3	434.6
0.50	63.00	0.4695	129.70	257.4	479.8

Thus Cd(II) forms three species : $[Cd(Nicotinate)]^+$, $[Cd(Nicotinate)_2]$ and $[Cd(Nicotinate)_3]^-$ with β_1 , β_2 & β_3 to be 20, 40 and 876, whereas Pb(II) forms two complexes species : $[Pb(Nicotinate)]^+$ and $[Pb(Nicotinate)_2]$ with β_1 and β_2 to be equal to 17.5 and 410 respectively. The complexes formed by Pb(II) are stronger than those formed by Cd(II). Polarographic behaviour of α -picolinate complexes with Pb(II) and Cd(II)^{1,2} revealed that α -picolinate forms much stronger complexes than nicotinate.

Alkali-Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Organic Acid with Oxygen and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Manuscript received 21 June 1976, revised 20 May 1978, accepted 8 September 1978

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In our earlier work, we have reported^{1,2} the synthesis of a large number of mixed ligand complexes of the general formula ML_nHL' , with 1-nitroso-2-naphthol as the second ligand, L' .

In order to study the coordinating ability of L' towards alkali metals, in the mixed ligand complex we are now extending this work by synthesising the adducts of alkali metal salts of some organic acids, (L), such as salicylic acid (SalA), 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (2H3NA), anthranilic acid (AnC), phenyl anthranilic acid (PhAnC), glycine (gly), β -alanine (Aln) etc., with 2-nitroso-1-naphthol (2N1N) (the second ligand L'), in which the nitroso group and the hydroxyl group are in the reverse position.

The derivatives of salicylic acid are of analgesic and therapeutic value. In order to have a comparative study of the donor properties of these acids, their alkali metal complexes have been synthesised with various nitrogen and oxygen containing second ligands.